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Bioadhesive Based on Lignin and Chitosan: A Study of Environmentally Friendly Advanced Application

Galia SHULGA^{*1}, Brigita NEIBERTE¹, Valerija KUDRJAVCEVA^{1,2},Arturs VIKSNA², Anrijs VEROVKINS¹, Talrits BETKERS¹¹Lignin Chemistry Laboratory, Latvian State Institute of Wood Chemistry, Riga, Latvia²Faculty of Medicine and Life Sciences, University of Latvia, Riga, Latvia*galshulga@inbox.lv, bricis46@inbox.lv, valerija.kudrjavceva4@gmail.com, artvik@inbox.lv,
anrivero@inbox.lv, betalrit@gmail.com

Abstract— This study demonstrates that a non-stoichiometric polyelectrolyte complex (NPEC) derived from birch soda lignin and chitosan can be successfully synthesized and applied as a sustainable structuring agent for sandy soil aggregation. The complex, formed through electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bonding between lignin and chitosan in the reaction mixture, exhibits favorable adhesive properties due to the presence of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic domains. These findings highlight the potential of this NPEC as an innovative, eco-friendly product for sustainable soil improvement and dust suppression.

Keywords: lignin, chitosan, non-stoichiometric polyelectrolyte complex, soil aggregation, water resistance

1. INTRODUCTION

The principles of the Circular Economy dictate the sustainable, rational, and efficient management of waste and by-products, as their annual volume increases markedly and negatively affects the environment. In contrast, waste recovery can provide a huge secondary resource for producing new materials and reducing their costs [1]. Lignin, a wood constituent, is a superbranched, phenylpropane-based amorphous polymer, in which its phenylpropane chains are bonded via ester, ether, and carbon-carbon linkages. It is the third most abundant polymer next to cellulose and chitin and comprises 25 to 30% of the organic substances on Earth. Technical lignins are by-products of pulp mills, combusted for energy generation. On the other hand, they have a great economic and industrial potential, and constitute the real challenge in obtaining eco-friendly value-added products [2, 3]. With this target, lignin is modified by hydroxyalkylation, esterification, alkylation, grafting with synthetic polymers and oligomers, etc. Their main drawbacks are the use of organic solvents, high applied temperatures, and pressure. Polyelectrolyte complexes (PECs) are self-assemblies with participant of anionic polyelectrolytes, including water-soluble lignins, and cationic ones due to the electrostatic interaction in aqueous media at room temperature, stabilised by H-bonds and hydrophobic interactions [4, 5]. The driving force of their formation is the gain in entropy caused by the release of low-molecular-mass counter ions due to electrostatic interactions. Due to their unique properties, PECs have multiple practical applications in various fields, namely, in medicine, packaging, for obtaining binders and other value-added products. Soil erosion and dust suppression are significant global environmental issues. Erosion reduces soil fertility, changes soil properties, and causes crop loss. Erosion under the weight of

transport traffic on unpaved roads increases the dust concentration in the air and leads to health problems. Traditional synthetic polymer-based soil stabilizers like polyacrylates and polyacrylamides are not biodegradable, and often washed away by rain [6]. Among bio-based soil stabilizers, lignin-based stabilizers have attracted considerable attention due to their renewability and environmental compatibility [7, 8]. The goal of this research was to study a non-stoichiometric polyelectrolyte complex formed with soda lignin and chitosan and to show its ability to improve sandy soil structure.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Soda lignin (SL) was obtained by the delignification of birch sawdust under laboratory conditions: NaOH concentration – 4.0%, temperature – 165 °C, and duration – 1.5 h. The content of Klason lignin in purified lignin was 93.9%. The chemical composition of the lignin was determined according to the TAPPI protocols. The weight-average molecular weight (Mw) of the lignin (SEC-MALS20) was 4120 Da. Commercial chitosan (Ch) has a deacetylation degree of 85 % and Mw - 400 kDa. Before using, it was diluted in acidic water solution. The non-stoichiometric polyelectrolyte complex lignin–chitosan (NPEC), with a charge ratio of $(n^-/n^+) = 1/1.3$ (SL/Ch), was prepared at room temperature by mixing equal volumes of aqueous solutions of the two biopolymers. The biopolymer concentrations ranged from 0.1 to 1.0 g dL⁻¹, and deionized (DI) water was used as the solvent. Artificial aggregates (> 0.25 mm) were produced by structuring sandy soil through manual mixing with NPEC solutions of defined concentration and application rate. Water resistance was assessed by determining the proportion of water-stable aggregates larger than 0.25 mm (wt%) remaining after the aggregated soil had been subjected to water treatment.

2.2. Methodology

The titration curves were obtained using a Radiometer Analytical Titrolab 90 (Radiometer Analytical SAS, France). The UV-VIS spectra were obtained using a Genesys 10UVUV/VIS spectrophotometer (Termo Fisher Scientific, USA). The size and zeta potential of the particles were determined using a ZETASIZER NANO ZS Malvern Instrument (Malvern, UK). FTIR spectra were recorded using a Nicolet iS50 spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) equipped with a diamond ATR crystal. The fractional composition and water resistance of the air-dry structured soil were determined by dry and wet sieving, respectively. For this measuring, a device mill “Pulverisette 0” (Frisch GmbH, Germany) was applied, using a set of sieves (AS200 Retsch).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Formation of non-stoichiometric polyelectrolyte complex

The results of the potentiometric and conductometric titration, spectroscopic, and viscometric data indicated that the mechanism of the interaction between soda lignin (SL) and chitosan (Ch) was complex and depended on pH. The titration curves (Fig. 1) showed that, in weakly acidic media, the interaction between the biopolymers was predominantly electrostatic in nature. This interaction led to the release of added protons into the reaction mixture as a result of charge regulation and the entropic driving force associated with complex formation. The relatively low UV absorbance of the SL–Ch reaction mixture at 280 nm and pH 5 (Fig. 2), together with its lower transmittance at 540 nm compared with those of the

Figure 1. Conductivity of 0.01 g dl solutions of SL, Ch and NPEC

Figure 2. UV absorbance of 0.01 g dl solutions of SL, Ch and NPEC

The ATR-FTIR spectra (Fig. 3) indicated that NPEC formation between SL and Ch in strongly acidic and neutral media was primarily driven by hydrogen bonding. This conclusion was supported by the decreased intensity and narrowing of the O–H/N–H stretching band in the 3400–3200 cm^{-1} region, the alignment and shift of the aromatic and amide bands in the 1700–1500 cm^{-1} region, the redistribution of band intensities in the 1300–1000 cm^{-1} region, and the reduced intensity of the C–H stretching bands in the 3000–2800 cm^{-1} region. These spectral changes suggest the involvement of aliphatic hydroxyl groups in the hydrogen-bonding interactions between the biopolymers.

Figure 3. ATR-FTIR spectra of air-dried soda lignin, chitosan and NPEC

According to the DLS measurements conducted in acidic medium, both soda lignin and chitosan exhibited bimodal particle size distributions. The first peaks in the size histograms corresponded to particle sizes of 591 nm and 539 nm, respectively, with relative intensities of 70–72%. In contrast, the NPEC particles were characterized by a dominant particle size of 251 nm with a comparable relative intensity. The approximately twofold reduction in particle size upon complex formation can be attributed to the compaction of the NPEC particles resulting from reduced electrostatic repulsion and enhanced

hydrogen-bonding and hydrophobic interactions between the biopolymers. Unlike soda lignin particles, the NPEC particles exhibited a positive surface charge.

3.2. Structuring properties of non-stoichiometric polyelectrolyte complex

Since the NPEC particles contained free functional groups (carboxyl, hydroxyl, and amino) located on the particle shell, as well as hydrophobic regions formed through electrostatic interactions between the biopolymers, these water-soluble particles exhibited binding affinity toward non-cohesive sandy soil.

Figure 4. Weight of soil aggregate fractions obtained by structuring sandy soil with the reaction mixture SL-Ch depending on its concentration and dosage (ml/100 g soil)

According to Fig. 5, increasing both the dosage and concentration of the NPEC solution enhances the aggregation of sandy soil. Higher concentrations and dosages promote the formation of larger soil aggregates (>5–7 mm). When a 0.5–1.0% NPEC solution is applied at a dosage of 30 mL per 100 g of soil, the aggregate content reaches 85–90%. The sandy aggregates formed after treatment with NPEC SL-Ch are also highly water-stable, exhibiting water resistance values of 75–80%.

4. CONCLUSION

The obtained results demonstrate that soda lignin and chitosan can form a water-soluble non-stoichiometric polyelectrolyte complex (NPEC) through the simple mixing of their aqueous solutions. Depending on the pH of the medium, the interaction mechanism between the two biopolymers may involve electrostatic attraction, hydrogen bonding, and hydrophobic interactions. The diverse functional groups present in the NPEC promote aggregation and adhesion to sandy soil particles, contributing to its soil-structuring capability. As a biodegradable material derived from renewable resources, the developed NPEC can represent an environmentally friendly and sustainable alternative to conventional synthetic polymer-based soil stabilizers.

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Author Contributions

The author read and approved the final version of the paper. This paper includes a part of a master's thesis supervised by the first author. They all read and approved the final version of the paper.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

Ethical Review and Approval

No ethical approval is required.

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